

Proceedings of the Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata (WOOC 2025)

Edited by

Ivan Heibi

(0000-0001-5366-5194)

University of Bologna

Chiara Di Giambattista

(0000-0001-8665-095X)

University of Bologna

Silvio Peroni

(0000-0003-0530-4305)

University of Bologna

Preface

The **Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata (WOOC) 2025** provides an international forum dedicated to advancing openness, transparency, and interoperability in research information. Organized by OpenCitations and hosted at the University of Bologna on 28–29 May 2025, the workshop convenes a diverse community of researchers, publishers, funders, institutions, and policy-makers to discuss current practices and to shape the future directions of open scholarly infrastructures.

The central theme of this year's edition is “**Open Access of Research Information.**” The first day is devoted to the *Bologna Meeting on Open Research Information*, a dedicated venue for signatories and supporters of the Barcelona Declaration to strengthen shared commitments, explore challenges, and define strategies for collective action. The second day is structured around invited talks, contributed presentations, and poster sessions, providing opportunities to showcase innovative approaches and to reflect on critical issues in the creation, dissemination, and reuse of open scholarly metadata.

WOOC 2025 is designed to foster constructive dialogue and collaboration across stakeholders, ensuring that discussions extend beyond technical and infrastructural concerns to encompass policy, governance, and community engagement. By bringing together leading voices and emerging perspectives, the workshop seeks to contribute to a sustainable, inclusive, and transparent scholarly ecosystem.

About the Workshop

Organizing Committee

- **Silvio Peroni**, *OpenCitations* | *University of Bologna, Bologna, Italy*
- **Chiara Di Giambattista**, *OpenCitations* | *University of Bologna, Bologna, Italy*
- **Ivan Heibi**, *OpenCitations* | *University of Bologna, Bologna, Italy*
- **Claudio Fabbri**, *OpenCitations* | *University of Bologna, Bologna, Italy*
- **Ludo Waltman**, *Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS), Leiden University*
- **Bianca Kramer**, *Sesame Open Science*
- **Cameron Neylon**, *COKI* | *Centre for Culture and Technology, Curtin University*

Program Committee

- **Sebastian Barzagli**, *University of Bologna*
- **John Chodacki**, *California Digital Library*
- **Giovanni Colavizza**, *University of Copenhagen* | *University of Bologna*
- **Angelo Di Iorio**, *University of Bologna*
- **Bianca Kramer**, *Sesame Open Science*
- **Catriona MacCallum**, *Future of Scholarly Research*
- **Andrea Mannocci**, *CNR-ISTI*
- **Arcangelo Massari**, *OpenCitations* | *University of Bologna*
- **Philipp Mayr**, *Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences*
- **Arianna Moretti**, *University of Bologna*
- **Valentina Pasqual**, *University of Bologna*
- **Francesco Poggi**, *University of Bologna*
- **Iratxe Puebla**, *Make Data Count, DataCite*
- **Matteo Romanello**, *University of Zurich*
- **Angelo Salatino**, *Knowledge Media Institute, The Open University*
- **Gianmarco Spinaci**, *University of Bologna*
- **Sahar Vahdati**, *Leibniz Universität Hannover*
- **Ludo Waltman**, *CWTS, Leiden University*

Bologna Meeting on Open Research Information (Day 1)

Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information. (2025). Report of the Bologna Meeting on Open Research Information. Bologna Meeting on Open Research Information, Bologna University, Bologna, Italy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15730917>

Invited speakers and OpenCitations talks (Day 2)

Di Giambattista, C., & Heibi, I. (2025). OpenCitations: an open infrastructure enabling Open Research Information. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17199853>

Skinner, K. (2025). Rapid-fire change, meet community action. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17199721>

Petti, S. (2025). We are building a world open by design where all knowledge is accessible to everyone. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17199789>

Contributions (Day 2)

Page, R. (2025). The grand challenge of data citation: a critical look at the Making Data Count Data Citation Corpus. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16320565>

Kubacka, T., Willemin, S., & Dederke, J. (2025). A 2-year retrospective into the open information landscape: Learnings from the TOBI project. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16323897>

Colangelo, E. (2025). Open Scholarly Metadata in Action: A Joint Effort of Infrastructure and Publishing. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16324164>

Levchenko, M., & Harrison, M. (2025). Enriching open metadata for preprints with Europe PMC. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16324401>

Zherebchuk, S., & Kudas, D. (2025). Capacity Building for Open Science: Ukrainian case study. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16324589>

Puebla, I., & Gould, M. (2025). Scaling open research information for scholarly outputs: The Data Citation Corpus advances evaluation of the impact of research data. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16324963>

Weimer, V., Shahid, M. A., Heck, T., Oerder, T., Mayr, P., & Schindler, C. (2025). Open Citation Data for Educational Research. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16325125>

Vergoulis, T., & Tatum, C. (2025). GraspOS Infrastructure: Enhancing Discoverability of Open Resources for Responsible Research Assessment. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17199517>

Malaguarnera, G., Manola, N., Grypari, I., Pispiringas, L., Manghi, P., Amodeo, S., & Tzouganatou, A. (2025). Advancing Open Research Information – Insights from the National Open Access Irish Monitor. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16363553>

Wake Hyde, Z., & Gatti, R. (2025). What's in a Book? A review of book-related work types in various metadata schemas, and an attempt to align these in OMP and Thoth Open Metadata. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16363755>

- Andreose, E., & Zilli, L. (2025). Investigating Bibliographic Entities Without Persistent Identifiers. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15722170>
- Bartlewski, J., Broschinski, C., Deinzer, G., Lang, C., Pieper, D., Schweighofer, B., Sippl, C., Stein, L.-M., Wagner, A., & Weisheit, S. (2025). Cost for research – how cost data of research can be included in open metadata to be reused and evaluated. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16364107>
- Caputo, A., Catalano, G., Duvaud, S., & Sousoni, D. (2025). The role of open data in driving innovation: insights from UniProt. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16364279>
- Di Iorio, A., Hubar-Kołodziejczyk, P., Romanello, M., Rosiński, C., Soricetti, M., & Umerle, T. (2025). OpenCitations for SSH: Improving OPERAS Metrics and Enriching Knowledge Graphs. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16364609>
- Marín-Arraiza, P. (2025). Enhancing research integrity with ORCID data. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16364857>
- Grypari, I., Bourdieu, S., Cole, N. L., Klebel, T., Papageorgiou, H., Príncipe, P., Ross-Hellauer, T., Stagiopoulos, P., Sousoni, D., Stoy, L., Traag, V., Tshipouri, L., Venturini, T., & Vignetti, S. (2025). The PathOS Project: Evidence, Methods, Tools and Lessons learned for Identifying the Impact of Open Science. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16365096>
- Bertozzi, A., & De Santis, L. (2025). Boosting data interoperability of GoTriple.eu. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16365509>
- Mannocci, A., & Manghi, P. (2025). Advancing Integration and Reuse Across Diverse Scholarly Data Sources. Introducing the SKG-IF: the Interoperability Framework for Scientific Knowledge Graphs. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16365716>
- Sandfær, M., & Lauridsen, N. D. (2025). Open - from local CRIS'es to global indexes and back: Creating a high- integrity national open research information and analytics platform in international collaboration. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16365913>
- Goeritz, M., & Steglich, P. (2025). Strengthening Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) in the Institutes of the Leibniz Association, Phase 2: Towards Open Research Information. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16366051>

- Fintoni, L. (2025). Making ontologies in the humanities more visible and accessible using SKOS. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16366316>
- Scalbert, S., Guha, K., & Romary, L. (2025). Open Access and AI for Research Assessment: Identifying and Evaluating Software Mentions in Scholarly Publications. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16366491>
- Bardi, A., Buzzoni, M., Daquino, M., Del Gratta, R., Angelo Mario, D. G., Fischer, F., Giacomini, S., Martignano, C., ROSSELLI DEL TURCO, R., Rubin, G., & Tomasi, F. (2025). FAIR Digital Humanities scholarly metadata. The ATLAS project. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16366693>
- Duran-Silva, N., Accuosto, P., Grimau, B., Bovenzi, N., Przybyła, P., & Saggion, H. (2025). Heterogeneous affiliation metadata enrichment with AffilGood. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16367023>
- van Eck, N. J., van den Boomen, B., & visser, . martijn . (2025). Accuracy of affiliation information in open bibliographic data sources: A comparative study of OpenAlex and OpenAIRE for Leiden University. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16367245>
- Montilla, L. M. (2025). Mapping Metadata Inequities: Regional Disparities in Crossref Scholarly Records. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16367370>
- Torny, D. (2025). Discovering and charting the black matter of citations. Matilda as a new source for Open Citations. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16367477>
- Martin, C., & Nathaniel, S. (2025). Preserving Scholarly Communications on the Web with Open Metadata. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16367574>
- sarin, . parth ., & Alperin, J. P. (2025). Citation Parsing and Analysis with Language Models. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16367716>
- Mietchen, D. (2025). Open Scholarly Metadata for Sharing the Nuances of Research Processes. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16367857>